

METAL NANOWIRES SELF-ASSEMBLY BY DIELECTROPHORETIC AND APPLICATIONS IN OPTOELECTRONICS

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ABSTRACT

This study presented a plasmonic solar cell with AuNR arrays upon the active layer to enhance the conversion efficiency. AuNRs in 20 nm diameters with aspect ratio of 20 were assembled into an array by an AC electric field generated by micrometer spaced electrodes which called dielectrophoresis force. The AuNRs increase light scattering and trapping in the silicon layers leading to enhancement of the external quantum efficiency. Additionally, the short-circuit current with appropriate design of electrodes is increased from 20.45 mA to 33.09 mA and the conversion efficiency is increased from 4.22% to 7.01% under the applied 20 Vpp.

1 INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaic cell is the promising technology to replace traditional thermal power plants for electricity generation. However, high reflectivity in the range of solar wavelength is disadvantageous to the employment of silicon-based solar cell, which results in large waste of useful sunlight by reflecting them back into free space. Take metal nanoparticles as components to increase the amount of incoming light is the great method without damage on surface of photovoltaic device.^[1,2,3,4] The enhanced field strength resulting from metal nanoparticles depends on the particle material, size and shape.^[5] Using simulated calculations, the results indicated that prisms, rods and spheroids with similar size dimension show similar enhancement on the scale of $> 10^3$, which is significantly higher than sphere ($\sim 10^2$).^[6,7]

For the metal nanoparticles, the alignment and assembling are simply completed by several approaches.^[8,9] However, to control over metal nanorods spatial position, various envisaged applications of nanorods demand control over their collective orientation in suspension and also after deposition at the substrate. Among various approaches^[10,11,12] of one-dimension nanomaterials manipulation, dielectrophoretic force has become increasingly popular due to the ability to fast depositing anisotropic nanorods precisely on a substrate, allowing integration with conventional top-down semiconductor processing.^[13]

2 EXPERIMENTAL

In this experiment, we use dielectrophoresis to make a spaced alignment of gold nanorods to avoid too close packed which will increase the reflection of substrate and result in negative effect on conversion efficiency of solar cells. In addition to spaced alignment of gold nanorods, dielectrophoresis force possesses advantages of rapid alignment as well. Therefore, by utilizing high aspect ratio gold nanorod^[14] to fabricate plasmonic structure via dielectrophoresis force is considered as a quite convenient, fast, and effective method to increase the efficiency of solar cells.

The basic device structure of Si-based p-n junction solar cell employed in this work is shown in Fig. (1). To form the shallow p-n junctions, phosphorous was implanted into the wafers by low energy of 10 keV and dense concentration of doping elements of 5×10^{15} ions/cm². After implantation, the substrates should be treated by annealing process of 1050°C and 10 seconds to eliminate the damage of materials during implantation. Based on this, various electrodes was designed and deposited upon the device by thermal evaporation to align AuNRs.

Figure 1. The plasmonic solar cell geometry.

Before utilizing AuNRs arrays on solar cell, preliminary experiment was designed to investigate the effect of voltage, gap, and material dimension on AuNRs alignment. Under this investigation, we applied these concepts on solar cell as component to enhance the conversion efficiency.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

On the preliminary experiment stage, to make AuNRs aligned, a sinusoidal ac voltage was applied to gold electrodes with various voltage and gap width to estimate the optimal results on various kinds of electrodes and three different dimension AuNRs. We began at short AuNRs (200 nm in diameter) assembled into the small gap width of 0.4 μm . As the result, AuNRs were aligned well parallel to electric field under voltages of 10 Vpp, 20Vpp, 40 Vpp. As shown in Figure 2, alignment of AuNRs demonstrated a much denser arrangement with the increase of voltages. We conclude that the high applied voltage resulted in more AuNRs trapped in the electrode gaps.^[15]

Figure 2. SEM images of assembled AuNRs with 200 nm in length in a 400-nm-width gap under various applied voltages of (a) 10 Vpp (b) 20 Vpp (c) 40 Vpp.

After aligning short AuNRs inside the small gap width, we turned the attention to investigate the assembling behavior of AuNRs on the larger gap width under applied electric field. The influence of voltage on the large electrode gaps was also examined. When applied voltage increased from 10 Vpp to 20 Vpp, well alignment of AuNRs parallel to the electric field direction was observed (Figure 3).

Figure 3. SEM images of assembled AuNRs with 400 nm in length in a 5-μm-width gap under various applied voltages of (a) 10 Vpp (b) 20 Vpp.

From Figure 2 and Figure 3, the effect of voltage on alignment was revealed. As can be seen in these images, AuNRs were deposited predominantly within the space between two electrodes near the electrode edges. For parallel plane electrodes, the electric field as well as the field gradient was large near the electrodes. Apart from bridging between the gaps, AuNRs were attracted more inside the gap. In addition to the dense attraction of AuNRs, the improvement of AuNRs alignment also observed when the applied voltages increased.^[16] The increase of applied voltages led to large magnitude and gradient of electric field. Large effective gradient of electric field contributed to large dielectrophoresis force acting on AuNRs. The increase of electric field also was contributed to large

torque motion.^[17] Therefore, accumulated AuNRs tended to aligned in uniform orientation parallel with the direction of electric field.

We continued to demonstrate the influence of AuNRs dimension on dielectrophoresis force. After the evaporation of AuNR droplet on electrode gap of 5 μm width, the accumulation of nanorods on the edges was also observed but without bridging between the pads. To bridge the wider electrode gap, shorter AuNRs should be replaced with longer one. AuNRs would undergo the large force under the same exerted voltage that on the smaller dimension. In addition to bridge the electrode gap, longer AuNRs aligned more parallel with the electric field as well.

Figure 4. SEM images of assembled AuNRs with the length of (a) 200 nm (b) 400 nm (c) 900 nm on the gap width of 5 μm under 10 Vpp applied voltage.

From Figure 4, the effect of AuNRs dimension was investigated. AuNRs with large volumes also benefit the alignment result. The dielectrophoresis force increased and alignment degree improved with volume of AuNRs enlargement.

In addition to small area, the substrates would be larger for further application on solar cells. In order to save the amount of gold nanorods usage, we put several individual 3 μl drops containing gold nanorods. Following we used a hydrophobic sheet to cover and pull with shearing direction leading complete coverage of gold nanorods solution and achievement of alignment. As shown in Figure 5, the alignment of AuNRs was achieved.

Figure 5. The SEM images of AuNRs alignment using shearing approach.

After achievement of these conditions, following we examined the effect of AuNRs array under different electrode gap width and compare with AuNPs array. It is found out that indeed increase of conversion efficiency with different degree under AuNPs and AuNRs array.(Figure 6)

Figure 6. J-V curve of AuNRs deposited on sample electrode which the finger widths and gaps were (a) 1 μm and 5 μm. (b) 1 μm and 20 μm. (c) 5 μm and 20 μm, respectively. J-V curve difference between AuNRs and AuNPs deposited (d).

The conversion efficiency of solar cell could be improved through light trapping by plasmonic nanoparticles.^[18,19] However, plasmonic nanomaterials offer a unique way to circumvent the inherent trade-off between absorption and carrier collection in the design of solar cells electrode. Therefore, it would enhance more under more appropriate solar cell design.

4 CONCLUSION

We could conclude that while the AuNRs aligned well on the comparable shorter gap width, increase of voltage brought about denser AuNRs attracted inside the gap. In the large gap width, AuNRs went through the trend of more parallel alignment and longer chaining with the increase of applied voltages. Combination of the spaced and ordered AuNR array and photovoltaic device reveals that the solar cell with plasmonic structure of AuNR arrays exhibited broad-band enhanced external quantum efficiency from invisible to near infrared wavelength region and current from 20.45 mA to 33.09 mA, with the increased efficiency of 62 %. In the future, with the help of the simulation, we would realize more about the mechanism of plasmonic solar cell with AuNR arrays and design more appropriate device to achieve greater enhancement.

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